

BIODT

biodiversitydigitaltwin

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D3.1 - BioDT Architecture and Implementation Plan

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Glossary of Terms

Item	Description
AAI	Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure
API	Application Programming Interface
CSC	CSC – IT Center for Science Ltd
DAG	Directed Acyclic Graph
DDI	Distributed Data Infrastructure
DestinE	Destination Earth
DiSSCo	Distributed System of Scientific Collections
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DT	Digital Twin
eIDAS	Electronic Identification, Authentication and Trust Services
eLTER	Integrated European Long-Term Ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological Research
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FDB	Fields Database
FDO	Fair Digital Object
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
HEAppE	High-end Application Execution Middleware
HPC	High-performance Computing
HPDA	High-performance Data Analytics

iRODS	Integrated Rule-oriented Data System
IT4I	IT4Innovations National Supercomputing Center
KTH	KTH Royal Institute of Technology
LifeWatch ERIC	e-Science European Infrastructure for Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research
OPeNDAP	Open-source Project for a Network Data Access Protocol
REST	Representational State Transfer
SSH	Secure Shell Protocol
TNO	The Netherlands Organisation for Applied Scientific Research
UFZ	Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research GmbH
UTARTU	University of Tartu
VM	Virtual Machine

Keywords

Architecture, Artificial intelligence, Biodiversity, Digital twin, FAIR, High-performance computing, Modelling, Prediction, Simulation

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Executive Summary

This plan describes the business and technical architecture of the digital twin platform that is being developed in the BioDT project, and outlines the process and envisaged timeline of implementing the platform. Further, the plan includes a vocabulary including working definitions of key technical concepts used by the BioDT consortium.

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1. Background

Biodiversity or biological diversity refers to the variety and variability of life on Earth. Biodiversity is important because it ensures food security, provides sources for medicine, offers economic benefits, holds cultural and aesthetic value, enhances ecological resilience, enables species evolution and adaptation, and carries ethical significance from the standpoint of preserving life. Biodiversity information is used to monitor ecosystem health, guide conservation efforts, and inform policy-making. It helps identify priority areas for habitat protection and evaluate the effectiveness of conservation measures, for example through monitoring shifts in the distribution of populations and communities of interest. Biodiversity data also supports sustainable land-use planning and natural resource management. Biodiversity is recognised in key EU and international policy initiatives, including the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030, EU Green Deal, UN Sustainable Development Goals, Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework and Destination Earth.

Biodiversity science is highly multidisciplinary, combining fields such as ecology, biology, genetics, economics and geography, which often tend to have a fairly short history of computational research. While traditionally simulations, modelling and data analyses in biodiversity research have not required substantial computing resources, biodiversity studies are becoming increasingly data-intensive [1], resulting in a growing need for approaches requiring the use of high-performance computing (HPC).

The Biodiversity Digital Twin (BioDT) project aims to push the limits of our understanding of biodiversity dynamics by developing digital twin (DT) prototypes that provide advanced modelling, simulation and prediction capabilities. The developed digital twins exploit the LUMI Supercomputer and employ FAIR data combined with digital infrastructure, predictive modelling and AI solutions. This document develops an open architecture for the digital twins and its reference implementation in the project. The development of digital twins is strongly driven by practical use cases and this architecture is created to synchronise the use cases.

Further, an important goal is to package HPC capabilities and FAIR data workflows into a form that is easily integrated into the BioDT use cases, streamlining the process of deepening the use of digital infrastructures.

1.1 Vocabulary

The following vocabulary defines key concepts used by the BioDT project consortium and, more specifically, in the description of the BioDT architecture. The terms are seen as working definitions, with changes anticipated in response to internal developments in BioDT and taking into account the wider European DT landscape. The definitions have been cross-checked for compatibility with the existing DestinE technical terminology¹.

1.1.1 Digital Twin

The BioDT consortium adheres to the following definition of a digital twin, based on a definition released by the Digital Twin Consortium²:

A digital twin is a virtual representation of real-world entities and processes, synchronised with real-world data at a specified frequency and fidelity.

Here, *fidelity* refers to the level of precision captured by the DT in comparison with its physical counterpart. *Digital twinning* refers to the process of designing and developing digital twins, and integrating them into their wider operational environment.

¹ <https://stories.ecmwf.int/destination-earth-glossary/index.html>

² <https://www.digitaltwinconsortium.org/>

<https://www.biodt.eu/>

The general goal of a DT is to serve as a digital replica that is sufficiently representative of its real-world counterpart (in terms of frequency and fidelity, and the scope and application of the DT) to reduce uncertainty about the real-world counterpart and take action for a specific purpose. Because of nonlinearities and gaps in system understanding, even the most realistic replicas, or models, can predict future developments only over a relatively short time horizon.

A digital twin is typically composed of:

- Data describing a real system
- A computational model that is the digital, or virtual, representation of the real system with regard to a specific purpose
- An application that connects the data and model in a way that makes the outputs of the model relevant, given the specific purpose of the DT
- Workflows that link the virtual representation and the real-world counterpart at regular intervals

Since even for the same system, different scopes require different representations, there cannot be a single twin answering all possible questions. Even so, not all DTs of a system need to be developed from scratch but can build on each other.

A typical purpose of *industrial* DTs is to facilitate the creation of a product or the operation of machinery. In BioDT, DTs are used to mimic behaviour observed in nature, with the purpose of developing an improved understanding of biodiversity dynamics in response to diverse human pressures, including climate change. To address this objective, BioDT will develop digital twins corresponding to several BioDT Use Cases. To maximise their usability and contribute toward the European Commission's goal of devising a full digital twin of the Earth³, the created twins can then be linked with or otherwise supplement twins developed as part of other DT initiatives.

1.1.2 Application

An action, information product or service which makes use of one or more digital twin services or outputs. Real-world applications of digital twins may vary depending on specific domain objectives and end-user groups. Depending on context, application may also refer to computing software designed to carry out a specific task.

1.1.3 Infrastructure

Infrastructure commonly refers to *e-Infrastructures* (i.e. computing and storage infrastructures) that enable digital twins to run, such as HPC infrastructures or cloud infrastructures.

Depending on the context, this may refer to:

- HPC clusters including LUMI supercomputer⁴. A HPC cluster is a collection of many computers (termed nodes) that are connected. LUMI's combined computing power, for example, is equivalent to that provided by approximately 1.5 million laptop computers.
- Hardware used by such clusters. This could, for example, refer to solutions for data storage or specific components and/or devices, such as graphics processing units (GPUs).
- Middleware software used by the previous. Middleware is a term for software enabling communication between otherwise separate applications.

³ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/destination-earth>

⁴ <https://www.lumi-supercomputer.eu/>

<https://www.biodt.eu/>

The term *infrastructure* can also refer to research infrastructures (RIs) which are entities that, for example, facilitate data collection, collation, storage, provision and findability. Four different biodiversity RIs (DiSSCo, eLTER, GBIF and LifeWatch ERIC) participate in the BioDT project.

1.1.4 Platform

In BioDT, a *platform* provides a layer of functionalities to be used for building and operating digital twins. A platform is built on top of infrastructure and cannot exist without infrastructure. A platform can be disambiguated into:

- Software components and interfaces for digital twinning. An example is an interface that sends information back and forth between a user and a service.
- Services and registries for hosting tools for data processing and analysis, and/or advancing research interoperability.

1.1.5 Workflow

Workflows can be disambiguated into:

- *Computational workflows* which refer to multi-step methods used to collect, process and analyse data, leading to new data products [2].
- *Data workflows* referring to the flow of data between different systems, storage locations and processing steps. A computational workflow can be a part of a data workflow. A data-driven workflow is often also called a *pipeline*.

There are many existing workflow systems that can help make workflow execution scalable, collect provenance and provide graphical interfaces. However, it is also possible to consider workflows implemented through scripts (e.g. Python, R) and notebooks (Jupyter).

When a digital twin features more than one modelling method or software, the term *digital twinning workflow* may be used to refer to a directed graph of interdependent models that need to exchange information in the correct order to achieve the purpose(s) of the digital twin.

By supporting the use of standardised approaches for process automation, workflow technologies are seen to hold considerable promise for improving the compliance of digital twins with FAIR principles [3].

1.1.6 FAIR and FAIR Digital Objects (FDO)

FAIR and FAIR Digital Objects (FDO) are principles used for sharing research outputs with structured metadata, making them machine-readable and actionable. In BioDT, the objective is to create and use digital objects that are *findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR)*. To achieve this, there is a need to assign persistent and unique identifiers to each object and describe them with sufficient metadata. These objects must be retrievable using open protocols and authentication where needed, and their metadata must persist even if the data is no longer available. Furthermore, they must use formal knowledge representation and vocabularies that are themselves FAIR and have qualified references to other data/metadata. The objects must also have a rich description with attributes and provenance, and they must follow domain-relevant standards. Some of these FAIR implementation efforts are already happening within each RI domain.

Being FAIR does not necessarily mean that the data must be open. In the BioDT project, authentication and authorisation will be implemented as needed using open and standard protocols. However, it is crucial to have explicit licences in place so that users can determine whether they are authorised to use the data. Additionally, core metadata must be open so that it can be indexed, and used for findability and machine-actionability.

The BioDT project employs the *FAIR Digital Objects (FDO)* framework. This approach involves treating each digital object (data, metadata, software, model, workflow, etc.) as a component that requires FAIRification. By treating each object as an FDO, it is possible to achieve modularity and flexibility in implementation and maintenance. For example, activities are undertaken in the project to consider adding structured metadata to existing digital objects, transforming data representation and serialisation formats to widely used formats like JSON or JSON-LD, and treating workflows as FDO using WorkflowHub and RO-Crate. An overall goal of applying FAIR principles to digital twins in BioDT is to enable the creation of machine-readable, reusable, and interoperable digital objects that promote collaboration and data sharing in biodiversity studies.

1.1.7 Provenance

Provenance is a structured way of explaining how some entity (real life or digital) came to be, its derivations and related activities (e.g. translating, analysing) and agents (persons, organisations, software), typically including timestamps and forming a *provenance chain*. Provenance is foreseen as part of the FAIR principles to ensure reusability of data and other FAIR Digital Objects. In the context of workflow provenance, the term *prospective provenance* typically refers to a workflow specification (i.e. a specification of a workflow one plans to produce). The term *retrospective provenance* is commonly taken to refer to a history log or dependency record of where the data lineage came from. FAIR standards for provenance include W3C PROV, PAV and RO-Crate, but many vocabularies also have key provenance terms.

1.1.8 Computational Model

A *computational model* is a formal representation of a problem or a process that is *a)* implemented via equations, algorithms or a combination of them, and *b)* can be executed by a computer to simulate, solve, or analyse the behaviour of the system under consideration. The term encompasses statistical and mechanistic models, as well as models that focus solely on the algorithmic and/or computational aspects of a problem. Multiple digital twins may use the same modelling methods or software. A single digital twin may also combine several modelling methods or software to achieve its goals.

Mechanistic models describe the development of a system over time. They are based on representations of mechanisms. *Statistical models* are based on correlations or other types of inferences made from data. *Machine learning models* comprise a specific type of statistical models.

1.1.9 Model Uncertainty

In BioDT, *model uncertainty* refers to the question of how well a computational model (see Section 1.1.8) relates to the origin, i.e. the physical counterpart of the digital twin. There can be various sources for model uncertainties. One source is that a model and the origin often share only specifically selected properties deemed to be of relevance (also known as truncation property). A model may, furthermore, be scoped to an ideal state of affairs (idealisation property) or may involve specific changes (distortion property) that need to be corrected when relating the model and origin. Other sources of model uncertainty are numerical instabilities or a biased set of training data for creating statistical models. In some cases, it may be possible to use uncertainty quantification techniques to obtain quantitative estimates of such uncertainties. Additionally, digital twins developed in BioDT do not directly feed back into sensors for the collection of state data (as is often the case in industrial DTs), therefore there is no sensor recalibration and uncertainty at the data layer is difficult to track.

1.1.10 Data Model

A *data model* is a specification for a data set. It typically specifies the structure of data sets, and the type and meaning of each element. It may also describe other properties of data, including content-related information (e.g. accuracy).

1.1.11 Use Case

In IT architecture work, *use cases* are defined to identify requirements for the architecture. In BioDT, a use case describes the context and example uses for a DT, including details on e.g. its scientific and applied rationale and envisioned impact, data sources, types and processing methods, the modelling methods employed, as well as the intended end-users and stakeholders. It defines the high-level goals, objectives and functionalities to be met by the digital twin.

1.1.12 Cloud Computing

Cloud computing refers to services, which allow for use of computational resources, based on cloud technologies. The resources may be provided by different resource providers including academic data centres and public cloud providers. Key features of cloud computing services are elastic resource provisioning and the control of the provisioned software environment. Cloud computing services are typically based on virtual machines or container orchestration solutions like OpenStack or Kubernetes, respectively.

1.1.13 High-Performance Computing

High-performance computing (HPC) refers to the use of computer systems based on a large number of compute nodes that are interconnected through a network system allowing for communication at high bandwidth and low latency. HPC systems are designed for applications and workflows that can be parallelised such that a large fraction (or all) of compute nodes can be used with high parallel efficiency. Parallel efficiency is typically defined as the ratio of serial execution time versus P times the execution time when using P compute nodes.

1.1.14 API

An *application programming interface* (API) is used in this document for defining interfaces for computer to computer communication. Any implementation of BioDT components is expected to comply with a given API definition.

1.1.15 Metadata

Metadata is data about the data, which is typically machine-readable. It plays an important role in implementing the FAIR principles as it, for example, contains information needed to make data findable and reusable by providing usage licence, data provenance information etc.

2. Architecture Vision

The main vision of the project is to provide digital twins for the wider public and to collaborate on a fairly generic environment for running digital twins related to biodiversity. The architecture is designed to support what we call a gradient of use cases. The simulation efforts behind the digital twins advance from fairly simple aspects of biodiversity to more complex scenarios. From an architectural point of view, we envision multiple fairly loosely connected digital twins which will be developed to be more connected and eventually merged, for example DTs of pollinators linked to DTs of grassland dynamics and management. However, the emergence of a single digital twin for biodiversity is not considered probable currently and therefore the architecture is built to support multiple diverse digital twins.

The architecture described in this document is guided by BioDT use cases. The use cases have led to high-level descriptions of BioDT DTs in terms of the following areas:

- Data
 - Inputs: Data sets and streams as well as tools for data ingestion
 - Outputs: resulting data sets, map layers provided via a GUI (etc.), according to the needs of the use case
- Model(s): The modelling method(s) used by the digital twin
- Users: Interfaces and tools for end-users

According to the descriptions of the use cases, APIs are required at two levels: one API should cover the receiving of data from the external data sources, including research infrastructures, and another API for interaction with the users:

- Interfaces for data access: Define how data is ingested into the BioDT platform and accessed by the models
- Front-end interfaces: Define how users access the models and interact with the results of the analysis

As an example on how data, models and users are described, Figure 1 shows a use case that integrates various data sources to feed data processing pipelines connected to the GRASSMIND model.

Figure 1 – General use case scheme for the use case “Grassland biodiversity dynamics”

The context where the use cases of the BioDT project are situated can be described by its major actors. They represent the key stakeholders or entities involved in the development, implementation, use and management of the biodiversity digital twins. They also play an essential role in the overall success of the architectural process by providing input, guidance, and decision-making capabilities. The purpose of defining major actors is to ensure that various perspectives, requirements, and concerns are considered and addressed throughout the architecture development process. Major actors of BioDT are given in the table below.

Actor	Description
DT Developer	Scientists and research software engineers that develop, implement, and test DTs
DT Operator	Personal role within the organisations in charge of operating the DTs
e-Infrastructure Operator	Personal role within the organisations in charge of providing computing, storage, and networking resources and related services
e-Infrastructure Resource Provider	Organisational entities that control resources that are made available as part of the e-infrastructure
Research Infrastructure Operator	Personal role within the organisations in charge of operating any of the connected Research Infrastructures. Some examples are: GBIF, eLTER, DiSSCo, LifeWatch ERIC.
Data Provider	Persons and organisations that are in charge of making data available that is accessible through the Platform or is consumed by the Platform. Currently most data is expected to come from the connected Research Infrastructures.
End User	Personal roles of scientists, policy-makers, citizens and other persons that connect to the DT front-ends

Table 1 – Key actors involved in the development, implementation, use and management of the biodiversity digital twins

Specific goals for the BioDT project to elaborate within different levels of the architecture include:

- Providing functionality to simplify and empower development and execution of digital twins for biodiversity
- Integrating with existing research infrastructures
- Integrating with cloud and HPC Infrastructures, specifically LUMI
- Federating data, models and applications between BioDT and research infrastructures
- Supporting BioDT FAIR Digital Objects which can have multiple instances and be distributed over multiple research institutes

The BioDT project co-exists with different RIs and initiatives, where some RIs are expected to provide input data, feed into use case design and development, or otherwise collaborate (e.g. through stakeholder interactions). There is also an alignment foreseen with important European initiatives, including Destination Earth (DestinE). The main players of the BioDT ecosystem are presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2 – Ecosystem surrounding the BioDT project

Establishing digital twins for a broad range of users (from citizens to government representatives and decision-makers) requires close collaboration between HPC experts, modellers and data owners. The digital twins and generic environment to run them, with all the complexity of integrating the components involved, requires a clear common architecture upon which the components to be included should be built on.

In the BioDT project, TOGAF (The Open Group Architecture Framework)⁵ has been selected as an approach to follow for elaborating a decent and suitable architecture, covering all aspects and facets of the provisional solution.

TOGAF is an [enterprise architecture](https://www.opengroup.org/togaf) methodology that offers a high-level framework for enterprise software development. It helps organise the development process through a systematic approach aimed at reducing errors, maintaining timelines, staying on budget, and aligning IT with business units to produce quality results. The TOGAF model is used in BioDT because the project involves many partners in different roles, introducing a level of complexity where many solution layers would be hidden without separating them into different architectural views level by level. The TOGAF modelling approach also makes it easier to align with the design methodologies used by different RIs and strategic initiatives. For example, Destination Earth uses the same approach.

⁵ <https://www.opengroup.org/togaf>
<https://www.biodt.eu/>

The architecture is defined as much as possible such that it can be deployed on top of compute and storage resources offered by EuroHPC JU. Furthermore, the design is such that BioDT services and data can become accessible through EOSC, and EOSC services and data can be used by the BioDT platform.

2.1 Envisaged Timeline of the Platform

When planning for the timeline of the platform, we have chosen to separate the platform into three levels:

- Open architecture: Technology agnostic description of the platform
- Reference implementation: Implementation of the open architecture delivered by the project
- Reference service: Service resulting from the reference implementation, operated by the project

The three levels have their respective timelines, so that focus of technical work progresses gradually through the levels. The envisaged timeline of the platform and its levels is outlined in the following:

- **Project month 11 (April 2023):** First version of open architecture completed.
- **Project month 16 (September 2023):** First digital twin available, based on the most mature use case. Parts of the reference implementation and reference service are available to the extent they are required by the first delivered digital twin.
- **Project month 24 (July 2024):** Reference implementation completed and released. Reference implementation allows the platform to be adapted outside of the project.
- **Project month 36 (May 2025):** End of the project, all three levels are completed. Reference service is documented to facilitate building service implementations that are independent of the project.
- **After the project:** Role of the BioDT project as a platform supporter ceases. Open architecture remains available for implementation using other technologies. Reference implementation remains available for deployment and modification (e.g. switching particular technologies). Reference service is not operated more, but all required material and documentation remains available for other service providers. The platform continues to be operational and is sustained as defined by a separate sustainability plan produced by the project.

All three levels see continuous updates also after they are initially completed.

3. Business Architecture

The business architecture for BioDT provides a blueprint representing a common understanding of how the project is positioned within the landscape of different initiatives, projects and research infrastructures dealing with biodiversity. It presents an overview of the roles and responsibilities of every partner and is used to align strategic objectives and demands to improve project performance. The roles defined within the BioDT project are related not only to immediate project partners, but also external stakeholders. Figure 3 outlines different stakeholder roles in relation to the project.

Figure 3 – Business roles defined for the BioDT project and envisioned interactions between them

The **Modeller** role belongs to modellers who are responsible for developing, training and providing digital twins identified in the BioDT use case descriptions. The role also includes acting as a highly advanced user of the digital twins under development.

The **Data Acquisition** role belongs to data providers of different types. This role foresees the activities to gather, prepare and share data sets required by scientists as model inputs. Some research infrastructures are also expected to have a Data Acquisition role.

This role in the BioDT consortium is attributed to: GBIF, eLTER, LifeWatch ERIC, TNO, all use case owners who define and request specific data sets, and selected entities external to the BioDT consortium, including Copernicus.

The **Compute Infrastructure** role involves provisioning the running environment for the digital twins under development, maintaining data sets used as an input to the digital twins, and maintaining data outputs produced by the digital twins. This role in the BioDT consortium is attributed to CSC (representing EuroHPC LUMI) and IT4I.

The role of **Research Infrastructures** represents a specific type of stakeholders, where aligning with the BioDT project is connected to the business goals of the infrastructure in question.

In BioDT, the Research Infrastructure role includes biodiversity RIs (LifeWatch ERIC, eLTER, GBIF, DiSSCo). The role is also attributed to Destination Earth.

The **Potential Users** role is taken to include different classes of future users of digital twins. Potential users who are foreseen to use biodiversity-related digital twins for decision-making include, for example, policymakers, land use planners, industry actors and citizens.

The development effort for digital twins related to such a complex domain as biodiversity, as well as elaborating the generic running infrastructure for such digital twins requires a collaborative effort from all the roles. A summary of collaborative efforts for different roles is presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4 – Collaborative efforts from multiple actors

Developing digital twins for predictive biodiversity modelling requires collaborative efforts from multiple actors. A shift in effort is also required to enable a transition from local developments toward establishing a re-usable, automated and generic running environment for digital twins, taking into account the responsibilities and business models of each actor. Estimated levels of effort (%) to enable this transition are shown for each business role defined within the BioDT project in Figure 4.

Streamlining the process of designing, implementing and using digital twins requires input from all stakeholders, ranging from compute infrastructures to modellers and potential users. For example, creating digital twins for biodiversity modelling requires collaboration between the Compute Infrastructure, Modeller and Data Acquisition roles, requiring an understanding not only of the needs of the immediate users, but also of potential users who should be considered already during the design and implementation process. When a digital twin is made operational, it should be hosted, maintained and extended according to the needs of Potential Users.

In the following, we discuss responsibilities established for every identified role and elaborate on new responsibilities and business opportunities during the development, deployment and use of digital twins as part of the BioDT project. The establishment and use of such twins is envisioned to enable new activities for every business actor, potentially leading to new responsibilities related to operating the digital twin. We

elaborate on the business role of each actor via storylines including details on current actions and responsibilities and what will change in the future via the operation of digital twins of biodiversity.

3.1 Modeller Storyline

Current responsibilities:

- Using research infrastructures to find, view and retrieve data
- Creating models and DT applications to perform analyses
- Storing new data at research infrastructures

New responsibilities where digital twins play a central role:

- Using metadata / registries of research infrastructures to find and retrieve applications and models (to build DTs and perform analyses)
- Making use of available generic applications and models to create DTs
- Using research infrastructures to execute DT applications and models
- Providing research infrastructures with new (preferably generic) DT applications for others to use

3.2 Potential Users Storyline

Current responsibilities:

- Funding and supporting research infrastructures to facilitate data collection, storage and findability

New responsibilities where digital twins play a central role:

- Funding research infrastructures for the collection and storage of applications and models for DTs and to improve their findability
- Funding computing infrastructures to support the execution of DTs (directly or via research infrastructures)
- Using DTs to monitor biodiversity (and store resulting data)
- Using DTs to perform biodiversity analyses for decision making
- Providing feedback for the further improvement of DTs

3.3 Research Infrastructures Storyline

Current responsibilities:

- Acquiring new related data sets
- Storing biodiversity data
- Storing results, making them available and findable (valid for some RIs)
- Making data queryable (valid for some RIs)
- Elaborating on process for data quality control (valid for some RIs)
- Enabling users to browse results (valid for some RIs)

New responsibilities where digital twins play a central role:

- Providing:
 - Building blocks for data acquisition by DTs
 - Experimentation environments for data analysis (HPC, cloud)
 - Standard methodologies for handling diverse models

- Means for an easy start and data visualisation as part of selected twins
- Supporting "flexible" twins that are capable of co-simulation

3.4 Data Acquisition Storyline

Current responsibilities:

- Acquiring new related data sets from different RIs
- Offering functionalities for real-time data provision and access to historical data
- Performing data pre-processing
- Performing data restructuring for specific uses
- Making data available and findable
- Introducing a data quality guarantee process
- Providing versioning/staging of datasets, where applicable
- Synchronisation with data sets undergoing changes in RIs
- Providing translations from one format to another
- Providing a single structural representation for all datasets (valid for some use cases)

New responsibilities where digital twins play a central role:

- Providing
 - Building blocks for data acquisition for DTs
 - Metadata storage
 - A common data model (for unified structural representation)
 - A toolset for pre-processing/cleansing/filtering
 - A quality measuring tool
- Operating synchronisation with external datasets
- Handling different subscribers for the same dataset, but for different purposes
- Providing synchronisation between different types of data (e.g. features, time series and spatial data)
- Developing capability for real-time data acquisition

3.5 Compute Infrastructure Storyline

Current responsibilities:

- Providing the isolated running environment for the models
- Supporting chosen programming languages
- Providing HPC and cloud-like computing capabilities to scientists
- Arranging data storage for input data and outputs of the models

New data-related responsibilities to support digital twins:

- Handling data from multiple diverse sources
- Supporting
 - Different data formats and conversions between them
 - Usage of agreed ontologies
 - Data catalogues with semantically defined metadata
 - Data querying and filtering
 - Sovereign sharing of data
- Providing a form of standardisation and/or data format and semantic translation (to allow generic usage of data by applications and models)

- Adhering to FAIR principles

New computing- and application-related responsibilities:

- Providing the platform for creating reusable applications and models
- Supporting APIs for applications and models (in order to enable their reuse)
- Consulting others on deciding which part of the applications and models should run on a laptop, in a cloud environment or a HPC platform
- Automating the deployment of DTs
- Supporting the deployment of models on cloud and HPC platforms
- Enabling parallelisation of models using cloud and HPC platforms
- Supporting the use of containerisation on HPC and cloud platforms

3.6 Summary of Storylines

From the storylines (Sections 3.1-3.5), it can be seen how biodiversity digital twins can result in many changes in responsibilities connected to different business roles, and bring about new business models. These potential envisaged changes, taken from all the storylines, are summarised in Table 2. For each responsibility, relevant stakeholders are identified by "X", with required actions described in brackets.

New responsibilities	Modellers	RIs	Data Acquisition	Potential Users	Compute Infrastructure
Develop generic components	X (develop applications and models)	X (develop or purchase applications; models, data, access and management / governance)			X (develop generic deployment components)
Use of generic components	X (use generic applications, models and data)	X (provide generic platform components for applications, models and data)	X (use generic components for data collection)		X (provide generic components for deployment)
"Fixed" twins for scenarios	X (use applications, models and data to build scenarios)	X (provide applications, models and data)	X (collect data)	X (support / fund DTs for scenario analyses)	X (provide processing)
"Flexible" twins for co-simulation	X (use applications,	X (provide federation of	X (collect data)	X	X

	models and data to build co-simulation)	applications, models and data)		(support / fund DT co-simulation)	(provide federated processing)
Automation to facilitate DT development and execution	X (incorporate automation as a part of DT development and execution)	X (develop and provide automation)	X (automated data collection)		X (automated deployment)

Table 2 – New responsibilities for different business roles after digital twins are deployed

The new responsibilities from different business roles and potential new usage scenarios were possible to summarise in five new classes of storylines (Table 2). The classes are further elaborated on in the following:

- **Development of generic components:** There may be changes in goals, requirements and modelling part of digital twins through their lifecycle. These changes may require the design and implementation of new generic blocks for digital twins as well as models.
- **Use of generic components:** Since digital twins could be re-used for making different decisions, the new usage scenarios can evolve in time. This means that the generic building blocks may need to be tweaked, tuned or reconfigured to suit new scenarios.
- **“Fixed” twins for scenarios:** A new scenario may require re-using a digital twin for a completely different purpose than the original purpose it was used for. This would require new efforts from different roles to make that new scenario work.
- **“Flexible” twins for co-simulation:** In certain situations, models/simulations may need to be run together and need to exchange information to reach a specific goal. This would require the digital twin to be designed in a flexible way, so that it becomes easy to couple different simulations/models and enable them to exchange information, where required by Potential Users.
- **Automation to facilitate digital twin development and execution:** For the efficient use and reuse of digital twins, a certain level of automation surrounding DTs is necessary. Ideally, a digital twin should automatically receive the data it needs, be possible to launch by the user in an automated way, and the results should be automatically saved.

Further to additional responsibilities, the deployment of new digital twins is foreseen to open up opportunities for different business actors that could also be used as new business models. Potential new business models resulting from the development and operation of digital twins in BioDT are presented in Table 3.

New business models	Modellers	RIs	Data Acquisition	Potential Users	Compute Infrastructure
Develop generic components for RIs	X (create new applications and models)	X (purchase or develop applications and models)		X (fund DT development)	

Collect data for DTs		X (receive or otherwise acquire data for DTs)	X (collect data for DTs)	X (fund DT development)	
Use DTs for biodiversity monitoring and analysis	X (use DTs for monitoring and analysis)	X (provide applications, models, data and platforms, including access, management and governance)	X (provide data for DTs)	X (fund DT operation)	X (provide processing for DTs)

Table 3 – Potential business models available after digital twins are made operational

In the following, the new business models outlined in Table 3 are described in further detail:

- **Develop generic components for RIs:** There could be changes in goals, requirements and modelling part of digital twins through their lifecycle. As a consequence, the development of new components, models, running environments, and coordination between the new components would be required. Developing and deploying modifications to existing DT components and extensions could therefore become a new business model for different business actors.
- **Collect data for digital twins:** The assimilation by DTs of new data, made available by RIs and other parties, could lead to a new business model involving the collection of new data and feeding it to an operational digital twin(s) in the correct format and at the required frequency.
- **Using digital twins for biodiversity monitoring and analysis:** The need to execute additional analyses (e.g. to compare new and old DT outputs) and provide additional modelling approaches as part of longer-term DT operation could establish new business opportunities related to the use of digital twins for biodiversity monitoring and analysis.

4. Information System Architecture Overview

The BioDT architecture aims to provide an abstraction layer over existing systems and services to satisfy the needs of the digital twin applications. An overview of the architecture is given in Figure 5.

Figure 5 – High-level presentation of BioDT components

The BioDT information system architecture is divided into several parts:

- **Users:**
 - **Anonymous** users accessing public components of BioDT.
 - **Authenticated** BioDT users accessing BioDT components. The concrete authentication and authorisation infrastructure depends on the component. For example, for BioDT Services, MyAccessID AAI (Authentication and Access Infrastructure) is planned, while applications hosted within BioDT Application hosting may use a different AAI system.
- **BioDT Public:** Publicly accessible catalogues of published BioDT artefact metadata, e.g. descriptions of BioDT workflows, datasets or used applications. We expect the objects exposed in this layer to be FAIR Data Objects.
- **BioDT Services:** Services accessible to authenticated and authorised users that provide an engine for execution of computational workflows as well as management of the required data.
- **BioDT Application Hosting:** Support services for hosting use cases for tools for BioDT applications.
- **BioDT Application Repositories:** External or internal repositories containing application artefacts (e.g. packages, container images or source code) used in BioDT applications.
- **BioDT Compliant Data Services:** External data services aligned with BioDT requirements for metadata and access, for example, services from research infrastructures.
- **BioDT Infrastructure Layer:** Collection of services at the facility where HPC/HPDA (high performance data analytics) services are located, along with components required for integrating with other parts of BioDT. This layer contains services that are mostly generic and not specific to the BioDT domain.

Section 5 provides an in-depth description of these parts, clarifying the concrete design solutions made.

5. Technical Architecture

The BioDT Technical Platform architecture follows a layered and modularised approach. We aimed at selecting concrete components based on existing services with sustainability models not solely dependent on the BioDT project. An overview of the components is given in Figure 6. In the following we go into details about each selected component and the role that it plays in the BioDT architecture. We start from the bottom layer and go up to the higher-level components.

Figure 6 – Main technical components and their place in the layered architecture

5.1 BioDT Infrastructure Layer

An important part of the BioDT infrastructure are the data centres which are operating HPC and/or cloud clusters that are provided to BioDT users in accordance with their operational policies.

The goal of our solution for the infrastructure layer was to introduce a minimal overhead to the modellers and specialists in HPC in terms of code execution on the infrastructure in specific data centres. This means

that specialists in HPC can help modellers to get their models running on HPC with a minimal modification, e.g. using the same bash script that they are used to, and it will be able to run in the data centres that have been integrated with the BioDT platform via HPC-as-a-Service approach described below.

Besides the computational clusters, a data staging area and integration with global resource allocation based on Puhuri are required.

5.1.1 HPC-as-a-Service

Usually, research HPC systems operated by organisations like CSC and IT4I have strict policies on the usage of HPC resources and security. A classic approach is to submit an application for compute time at the given HPC centres, for example through EuroHPC or local open calls, after that, a personalised user account is created and access to the supercomputer is granted usually through the SSH protocol.

To alleviate the last part, several HPC-as-a-service solutions were created. In BioDT we are planning to leverage the HEAppE Middleware⁶ solution. HEAppE provides necessary functions for job management, monitoring and reporting, user authentication and authorisation, file transfer, encryption, and various notification mechanisms through REST API. External user accounts do not have direct access to the HPC infrastructure itself. They are used only to authenticate the external user via HEAppE middleware to access only HEAppE's provided functions. External user accounts can be managed directly via HEAppE i.e. stored within HEAppE's internal database or handled externally by some external AAI. HEAppE provides the mapping between an external AAI and internal HPC centre AAI (e.g. LEXIS Platform AAI). It keeps track of which service account was used for the submission of which compute job and which user made the submission.

To fully leverage the [LEXIS Platform](#), it is possible to expose changeable parameters in the modellers' scripts by adding so-called HEAppE parameters to the scripts. These variables are then exposed to LEXIS and users can change them during the workflow run definition.

5.1.2 High-Performance Computing cluster

High-performance computing clusters usually operate a specialised batch scheduler such as SLURM or Altair PBS, and a filesystem specialised on operating on many nodes (the LUMI supercomputer uses Lustre). Typically, at the HPC centres there are strict rules on the usage of resources as well as for the deployment of applications. These are, for example, that users must work only in user-space without the ability to gain administrative rights. This can make deployment of specific software difficult. Usually, there is no resource sharing on the nodes, but this rule depends on the centre policies and especially for the GPU nodes with multiple GPUs, it may be possible to gain access to only part of the GPUs at the node instead of blocking of the whole node, when it is not needed.

5.1.3 Cloud

Many applications need more flexible resource configurability or need to execute smaller applications such as data pre/post processing or visualisation services. In this case the HPC batch system is not the optimal solution and usually a cloud operating container or VM oriented frameworks such as Kubernetes or OpenStack are complementary to the HPC clusters. Usually these systems are backed by the large Ceph or similar storage clusters. In terms of BioDT, LEXIS OpenStack cloud with on-demand Kubernetes clusters operated at IT4I will be available, as well as OpenStack and Ceph based systems at LUMI/CSC.

⁶ <https://heappe.eulink>
<https://www.biodt.eu/>

5.1.4 Data Staging

During the execution of the BioDT workflows there will be a high volume of data movement from the external data services, between tasks of a given workflow and also when submitting the results to open repositories. To manage these tasks and speed up the process for a large dataset a data staging zone at the compute centre will be set up. This staging zone can be used for the secure storage of the partial results during the computation, or to transfer data in between tasks. Currently, the LEXIS Platform has a data staging built around the Integrated Rule-Oriented Data System (iRODS)⁷. As a result of having iRODS zones deployed at every centre using the LEXIS Platform, it is possible to easily move or replicate data between the iRODS zones and provide a secure and fast way to work with data. Since the staging zone should be connected to the HPC or cloud systems by a very fast connection, the staging zone can also be used to “cache” frequently used datasets, so they do not need to be downloaded from the external services, thus speeding up the workflow significantly while reducing the network bandwidth usage.

5.2 BioDT Services

In BioDT we aim to create a set of APIs to work with individual biodiversity digital twins. In the first phase, these services and APIs should provide users with the ability to:

- Manage their data (upload data, download data, publish data)
- Execute BioDT use case computations
- Track user-specific executions
- Provide reproducible workflow execution descriptions

The LEXIS Platform⁸ was identified as a suitable tool to serve as the basis for most of these services. By integrating the LEXIS Platform with Puhuri⁹ and extending its functionalities through the provision of a FDO layer¹⁰, it should be possible to implement a system that covers the desired services and exposes desired APIs to the users.

5.2.1 Workflow Management and Orchestrator

Digital twin execution is usually not just a simple single command execution, but a more complicated set of tasks that together create a workflow. These tasks can in most cases be described by a directed acyclic graph (DAG). Workflows represented as DAG can be then executed on computational infrastructure. An important requirement for us is the possibility to orchestrate tasks on HPC batch scheduling systems and also on cloud schedulers. These functionalities can be achieved by using for example YORC orchestrator with HEAppE plugin installed, or Apache Airflow with custom provider and plugin installed which uses HEAppE for HPC task execution. In BioDT we expect to use the LEXIS Platform and its Apache Airflow workflow manager. It is important to note that for modellers, Apache Airflow will be abstracted in a LEXIS high-level workflow description. That means they will only need to supply high level descriptions of their workflow and its tasks. Technical details such as container deployment, HPC task low level definitions, etc. will be hidden, but still possible for power users.

⁷ <https://irods.org/>

⁸ <https://docs.lexis.tech>

⁹ <https://puhuri.neic.no/>

¹⁰ The FDO layer implementation plan for the RIs will be delivered by May 31, 2023.

<https://www.biodyt.eu/>

5.2.2 Distributed Data Infrastructure Core

The first version of the BioDT Technical Platform is expected to be running on the LUMI supercomputer, leveraging the newest possible hardware, but the long-term view is to support multiple data centres, and make it possible to use BioDT on multiple locations. To support this, a distributed data infrastructure is needed. Besides support for multiple centres there are other requirements that the data infrastructure must provide unified, reliable access to the data stored on multiple systems with different storage technologies and also support unified AAI. An example of a technology covering these issues is iRODS, with multiple plugins such as the iRODS-OpenID plugin being available for AAI support. The LEXIS platform has the DDI (Distributed Data Infrastructure) system built atop iRODS and uses Keycloak for the AAI. Elasticsearch is used to quickly query datasets metadata, stored in the LEXIS DDI system.

5.2.3 Backend

Since the final solution may be deployed at multiple locations, it is necessary to keep information about the LEXIS users, their roles, projects, organisations, etc at a central place that is secured and operated on a dedicated location. The backend service is a secure REST API on top of an extensive database schema which allows the platform to store information about workflow executions, application parameters across locations and thus track the entire lifecycle of a computation workflow. Thanks to this service, it is also possible to replicate execution of a workflow with the exact same parameter settings and input data.

5.2.4 Security

A consistent security model in the applications, infrastructure components and user rights definition is mandatory, as some use cases (e.g. disease transfer from wild boars to domestic pigs) have sensitive data. Moreover, the HPC providers participating in BioDT require a high level of security and identity assurance. Here we describe the security solutions for the common architecture and shared by all use cases, but many use cases will also add their own specific security measures that are not in the scope of this architecture (e.g. an AI method for filtering out human voices from audio recordings in the bird tracking use case).

The LEXIS Platform is built based on the “zero trust” concept and “security by design” principles. It tries to minimise the attack surface area and provide sensible identity and access management. The architecture is modular, with communication realised by REST APIs, and using a zero-trust security policy based on the modern OAuth2 protocol, with custom role-based access management handled by the Keycloak service. The service also allows the LEXIS Platform to easily integrate with other identity providers such as MyAccessID¹¹ via the Puhuri AAI Identity proxy. The platform also implements its own identities in the AAI module and remains compatible with local HPC centre identity and project management through the HEAppE middleware. In BioDT, we will strive to build atop the LEXIS Platform and keep this high level of security standard in the provided services. This approach also includes the utilisation of the so-called Secure Vault solution that represents a secure storage/password vault/password manager to store usernames and password or access credentials in general for external applications in a secure and encrypted way.

The issue of keeping in sync of local site accounts and global cross-site identities is planned to be resolved using Puhuri services. Puhuri is providing allocation info to data centre sites as well as membership info using global identities with a high level of assurance. The data centre sites can then create local accounts either using suggested usernames or generate their own based on the global account data and propagate back. Additionally, the generation of robot and group accounts is supported, which allows for creation of ‘gateway’ nodes with HEAppE middleware to be created easily.

¹¹ <https://wiki.geant.org/display/MyAccessID/MyAccessID+Home>
<https://www.biodt.eu/>

5.2.5 Authentication and Resource Allocation

BioDT relies on Puhuri¹² for providing a global authentication and resource allocation service. For an overview of Puhuri services, see Figure 7. In particular, Puhuri’s AAI provides access to a larger number of identity providers from MyAccessID¹³, including academia, eIDAS, community providers as well as solutions for industry users with a goal of assuring the high level of assurance for the identities. These Puhuri Identities are then used for managing membership of users in global projects that can include allocation at multiple HPC sites, with membership information kept in Puhuri Core.

Beyond identities and project information, Puhuri is providing reporting and statistics that also supports usage data reported by HPC sites.

An important extension in the context of BioDT provided by Puhuri is the ability to generate ‘group accounts’ on allocations that represent one or more identities as well as could include custom credentials, e.g. SSH keys. Such a functionality is important for easier integration of HEAppE that relies on the availability of pool accounts for job orchestration.

Integration with Puhuri is intended to be as non-intrusive as possible and aimed to complement the existing allocation policies and procedures of HPC sites, while providing a common abstraction layer that higher order orchestrators like LEXIS can rely upon.

Figure 7 – Summary of Puhuri services

On the technical side, we plan to connect Puhuri with BioDT Services in the following way:

- On the BioDT Platform layer, by directly integrating the LEXIS platform for discovery of allocations and requesting resources on different sites with Puhuri Core. We will also integrate LEXIS with Puhuri AAI to get global identities.

¹² <https://puhuri.neic.no/>

¹³ <https://wiki.geant.org/display/MyAccessID/MyAccessID+Home>
<https://www.biodt.eu/>

- On the HPC-as-a-Service side, we will integrate Puhuri agents with a batch scheduler (SLURM in Figure 8) for pulling and syncing allocation information from Puhuri Core.
- A robot account manager is an optional component in case robot accounts are required by BioDT use cases.

The above integration plans are summarised in Figure 8.

Figure 8 – Example of a planned integration of Puhuri for authentication and resource allocation with an HPC site based on SLURM

5.3 BioDT Application Repositories

Since we are striving to be as reproducible and open as possible, we expect most of the components created as part of the BioDT to be stored at specific repositories with some connection to BioDT. These may be public repositories, or if needed also specific private repositories for sensitive and confidential content.

5.3.1 Workflow Registry

Each of the BioDT use cases shall create their own workflow. These workflows shall be stored at WorkflowHub¹⁴. Some of the BioDT teams at WorkflowHub are already created¹⁵. An advantage of

¹⁴ <https://workflowhub.eu>

¹⁵ <https://workflowhub.eu/programmes/22/projects?view=default>

WorkflowHub is its support for git repository integration, bioschemas for published metadata about workflows, Common Workflow Language, FAIR Digital Research Objects in the form of RO-Crates, workflow systems such as Galaxy, DOI, snapshotting and more.

5.3.2 Container Repositories

We expect that some parts of the BioDT workflows will leverage containers such as Docker or Apptainer, and these may be stored at container repositories such as DockerHub, GitHub container registry or others.

5.3.3 Code Repositories

Code for the Use Case models and other scripts is expected to be stored in the code repositories. BioDT has already set up its organisation at GitHub (<https://github.com/BioDT>) and will publish Use Case codes there, as well as other application codes created as part of the BioDT. Some other codes related to the BioDT may be hosted at organisation specific GitLab repositories, where their continuous support will be guaranteed.

5.3.4 Specific Private Repositories

Besides other repositories, it is possible that BioDT will use specific private repositories to store sensitive or confidential codes, container images, or data. The BioDT Technical Platform architecture design is capable of supporting such cases where required.

5.4 BioDT Application Hosting and BioDT Compliant Data Services

Digital twins created in BioDT will rely heavily on the data providers like GBIF or eLTER or other digital twins like those developed under Destination Earth. The BioDT platform will have to support the relevant APIs and tools to facilitate data transfer from/to these research infrastructures. We call such services BioDT Compliant Data Services. Data exchange may require operation of specific services, e.g., for aggregating different data streams through an OPeNDAP (Open-source Project for a Network Data Access Protocol) Cloud Server that can be executed as part of the BioDT Application Hosting. Integration to Destination Earth could be based on the FDB (Fields Database) object store, which is a rolling archive for high-resolution output of DestinE digital twins and a long-term indexed store of meteorological data. DestinE looks to optimise data access and FDB transfers outside of the DestinE architecture could be discouraged, which needs to be taken into account in the BioDT integration.

The BioDT Compliant Data Services should support the necessary functionality for complying to FAIR principles, e.g. support of data provenance and reproducibility.

5.5 BioDT Public

Although many services in BioDT will be available only to registered users, since they are based on computational resources which need to be audited, some parts will be publicly available. These should be mainly metadata about the workflows, datasets and a catalogue of the applications available in BioDT. Any user will be able to browse through these metadata without a need to login to the service.

6. Implementation Plan

The implementation of the technical platform will be done in an incremental and iterative process in synchrony with the gradient of use cases. We recognise the inherent difficulty of building fully fledged digital twins for the complex and loosely bounded phenomenon of biodiversity. Hence, the process of devising digital twins needs to be designed to be self-correcting. The technical platform will therefore be built on increments, so that experience and feedback from a previous increment is available and used to guide the development of the forthcoming increments.

The incremental development of the platform is driven by the gradient of use cases, as depicted in Figure 9. By initially focusing on a less complex use case while building on an existing technological stack, we can cut down the lead time of the first prototype and thus maximise the time available for incremental further iterations. This way the later prototypes can benefit from the accumulation of know-how from the earlier ones.

Figure 9 – Iterative process for working on gradually more demanding use cases

The implementation timeline of the platform can be described in terms of three separate levels:

- **Open architecture:** Technology agnostic description of the platform
- **Reference implementation:** Implementation of the open architecture delivered by the project
- **Reference service:** Service resulting from the reference implementation, operated by the project

The planned phases of the platform implementation work are:

- **M3-M8:** Setting up infrastructure for the reference service
- **M7-M11:** Creation of open architecture
- **M11:** Completion of Architecture and Implementation Plan (Deliverable)

- **M12-M16:** Implementation of core parts for the reference implementation, guided by pilot use cases; setting up the reference service
- **M16:** First Digital Twin as a Service Available (Milestone)
- **M17-M24:** Further development of the reference implementation toward a first full version, guided by all use cases
- **M24:** Reference implementation release (Deliverable)
- **M24:** Additional HPC site Is Connected to the Reference Service (Milestone)
- **M24-M36:** Continued development of the reference implementation, matching new emerging needs from sustainability planning

The implementation of the platform can be divided into the following main actions. The actions and responsible consortium partners are described below. For actions related to the reference implementation of the platform we list key technologies, whereas for actions related to the reference service we list key infrastructures to be used.

- Open architecture
 - Responsible partners: CSC, UTARTU, IT4I, TNO, KTH
- Access and resource management implementation
 - Responsible partners: UTARTU
 - Key technologies: Puhuri
- Distributed data infrastructure core implementation
 - Responsible partners: IT4I
 - Key technologies: iRODS, LEXIS
- Workflow management and orchestrator implementation
 - Responsible partners: IT4I
 - Key technologies: LEXIS
- BioDT service API design and implementation
 - Responsible partners: IT4I, UTARTU, CSC
 - Key technologies: TBD
- HPC-as-a-Service API implementation
 - Responsible partners: IT4I
 - Key technologies: HEAppE
- Data service integration implementations
 - Responsible partners: TBD
 - Key technologies: TBD
- Application repository implementations
 - Responsible partners: TBD
 - Key technologies: Git, Gitlab
- BioDT service API deployment
 - Responsible partners: IT4I
 - Key infrastructure: LUMI cloud, other cloud infrastructures
- Application hosting service deployment
 - Responsible partners: CSC, IT4I
 - Key technologies: LUMI cloud, Pouta, IT4I cloud
- HPC deployments
 - Responsible partners: CSC, IT4I
 - Key infrastructure: LUMI, Karolina
- Cloud deployments
 - Responsible partners: CSC, IT4I
 - Key technologies: LUMI cloud, Pouta, IT4I cloud

- Distributed data infrastructure zone deployments
 - Responsible partners: IT4I, CSC
 - Key technologies: iRODS

The breakdown into actions reflects the current situation and is likely to evolve as the development of the platform progresses. Platform development is tracked internally within the project and an up-to-date status of the progress is maintained by frequent meetings and using an issue tracking system.

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